

Non-Faradaic Electrolysis in Presence of Depolarisers*

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Electrolysis of an aqueous 0.001N Na_2SO_4 solution in presence of various organic and inorganic depolarisers at anode and/or cathode has been studied. In presence of an adequate concentration of depolariser no gas is liberated at depolariser—reactive electrode, whereas the gas volume at the other electrode is nearly Faradaic with no or a little co-liberation. Various theories of non-Faradaic electrolysis postulated so far have been discussed and it has been shown that the present study lends some support to the theory of charged water migration, though these results cannot be regarded as a crucial evidence for the same.

It has been amply demonstrated by one of the authors^{1,2} that at low concentration and low current density the results of electrolysis show a number of anomalous features (termed non-Faradaic electrolysis), the most striking of which is co-liberation. This means that the gas liberated at the cathode as well as that at the anode is a liberal mixture of hydrogen and oxygen which usually explodes on sparking.

The cause of this highly unexpected behaviour is not at all understood though a number of suggestions have been made³⁻⁶. The basic question is whether such mixtures are liberated *ab initio* at the respective electrodes or they originate through inter-electrode migration of some kind. The results reported in the present paper are intended to throw some light on this question.

Experimental

Our electrolysis cell is a simple U-tube (1 ft high and 32 mm OD) having provision for insertion of electrodes and gas collection from the top (Fig. 1). Such type of cell is convenient for keeping the electrodes quite apart in order to prevent any possible inter-electrode diffusion of gases. This is connected in series to a coulometer containing normal potassium sulphate to measure the theoretical Faraday volumes (V_{FC} and V_{FA}). Power is supplied either from the D. C. mains (230 volts) or from a D. C. power supply unit. Usually the amount of current passed is 1 mA to 2 mA. Therefore it is allowed to run uninterrupted for a day or two so that a fairly large volume of gas ($V_C = 50$ cc or more) is collected. Samples of gas are withdrawn and analysed by sparking. From the contraction in volume (both for explosive and non-explosive mixtures) the oxygen content of the cathode gas and hydrogen content of the anode gas are calculated. Bright platinum foil (1 cm^2) electrodes were used in all cases.

In our first series of experiments a solution of 0.001(N) Na_2SO_4 containing 5 to 50% ethyl alcohol has been used. Similar electrolyses have also been done with addition of ethylene glycol, glycerol and 40% formaldehyde. Finally few experiments are done by using ethyl alcohol, glycerol and glycol at the anode compartment only, the cathode side containing only distilled water. Reverse is done with the formaldehyde solution.

Results and Discussion

The results obtained in various experiments are shown in Table 1. The notable features of our results are briefly described below :

(1) 0.001(N) Na_2SO_4 without any additive :

At 2 mA current density, both cathode gas (V_C) and anode gas (V_A) are less than the corresponding Faraday volumes, and are explosive mixtures of hydrogen and oxygen. Moreover, the ratio between the cathode gas and the anode gas is greater than 2.

(2) Ethyl alcohol as additive :

(a) 0.001(N) Na_2SO_4 with 50% ethyl alcohol—Pure hydrogen is liberated at the cathode and is equal to V_{FC} but the anode gas is almost nil which is evidently due to oxidation of alcohol.

(b) 0.001(N) Na_2SO_4 with 10% ethyl alcohol—The results are more or less similar to the previous one.

(c) 0.001(N) Na_2SO_4 with 5% ethyl alcohol—In this case V_C and V_A are less than V_{FC} and V_{FA} and are explosive mixtures of hydrogen and oxygen. Evidently mere 5% alcohol is not enough to suppress co-liberation, it being consumed (oxidised) at least

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Fig. 1.

near the anode long before the interruption of electrolysis.

(3) 0.001(N) Na_2SO_4 with 50% and 10% ethylene glycol :

The results are more or less similar to those in the previous case.

(4) 0.001(N) Na_2SO_4 with 10% glycerol :

V_C is slightly less than V_{FC} but without any co-liberation and no gas appears at the anode.

The comparative volumes of H_2 and O_2 vis-a-vis Faraday volumes obtained at each electrode in the above experiments are graphically presented in Fig. 2(A).

Fig. 2. A=Electrolysis of 0.001N Na_2SO_4 in presence of different organic compounds as depolariser.

B=Depolariser at one of the electrodes only, when the other side contains distilled water.

a=Ethyl alcohol, b=Ethylene Glycol, c=Glycerol, d=Formaldehyde, e=Potassium iodide, f=Copper sulphate.

(5) Additive at one of the electrodes only :

(a) 10% ethyl alcohol at the anode side and distilled water at the cathode side—No gas is

TABLE 1—RESULTS OF ELECTROLYSIS IN PRESENCE OF ADDITIVES; ELECTROLYTE USED=0.001N Na_2SO_4 , CURRENT DENSITY= ~ 2 mA., VOLTAGE INPUT=44 to 250 VOLTS

Additive used	Cathode gas		Anode gas	
	Anode	% V_C/V_{FC} % O_2 in V_C	% V_A/V_{FA}	% H_2 in V_A
50% Ethyl alcohol		100	Nil	No anode gas
10% Ethyl alcohol		100	2	4.4 1
5% Ethyl alcohol		95	8	19.8 23.6
50% Ethylene glycol		100	2.6	No anode gas
10% Ethylene glycol		92	trace	5 24
10% Glycerol		93	nil	10 42
40% Formaldehyde 0.001N Na_2SO_4		No cathode gas	90	nil
Distilled water	10% Ethyl alcohol	100	nil	8 nil
"	10% Ethylene glycol	100	nil	No anode gas
"	10% Glycerine	70.5	nil	No anode gas
"	N/10 KI	100	nil	No anode gas
N/10 $CuSO_4$	Distilled water	No cathode gas	91	nil
Distilled water*	20% Ethyl alcohol	100	nil	No anode gas

* Electrolysis carried out at 40°C.

liberated at the anode. V_C is equal to V_{FC} and oxygen free.

(b) 10% Ethylene glycol at the anode side and distilled water at the cathode side—Results similar to the previous experiment are obtained.

(c) 0.001(N) Na_2SO_4 at the anode side and 40% formaldehyde at the cathode side—Results are very much different in this case. No gas liberates at the cathode, and V_A though less than V_{FA} is pure oxygen.

(6) *Inorganic salts as depolariser :*

Results similar to above are also obtained when various inorganic salts are used as depolariser. For example, during electrolysis with copper sulphate, silver sulphate, zinc sulphate and potassium iodide, etc., at sufficient concentration (say N/100), no co-liberation appears so long the metals get deposited at the cathode or iodine gets liberated at the anode.

Even at 40°, where high percentage of co-liberation is a usual phenomenon⁷, electrolysis of (N/10) $CuSO_4$ at the cathode side and distilled water at the anode side shows no trace of hydrogen in the anode gas or oxygen in the cathode gas.

The results of expt. Nos. (5) and (6) can be had at a glance from Fig. 2(B).

From the above results we are now warranted to conclude that though under the conditions of low electrolyte concentration and low current density, co-liberation takes place, the picture changes completely when a depolariser is present in sufficient concentration. In the latter case there is no co-liberation at the other electrode; and there is no or a very little gas liberation at the electrode where the depolariser is present. But with insufficient concentration of depolariser or with no depolariser at all, co-liberation takes place as usual. These results are significant and appear to be of interest in understanding the cause of co-liberation as discussed below.

Theory—Different theories have been suggested to explain the non-Faradaic behaviour particularly co-liberation. They are listed below: These appear to run counter to experimental facts and this aspect is discussed below.

- (I) Inter-electrode diffusion of the liberated gases⁴.
- (II) Discharge phenomenon near the electrode surface; voltage induced decomposition of water; production of energised water and its subsequent decomposition, etc.^{5,8}.

- (III) Counter-charging followed by reverse migration of the liberated gas atoms, molecules or microbubbles⁵.
- (IV) Theory of charged water formation followed by migration^{1,2}.
- (V) Electronic conduction^{1,2}.

(I) From our results it may be conceived that the idea of inter-electrode diffusion is the only cause of co-liberation, since no co-liberation takes place in absence of gas liberation at the other electrode. But there is no reason why no hydrogen appears at the anode when there is no oxygen present due to the addition of depolariser. Another strong objection against the diffusion theory is that it fails to explain why increase of concentration tends towards Faradaic behaviour. Besides, it is difficult to see how diffusion can take place even when an inter-electrode distance of as large as ten feet or even more is used.

(II) The theories lumped under (II) though attractive, however, have one difficulty in common. If water decomposes, the total gas must be more than that stipulated by Faraday's law as in glow electrolysis⁹. Generally we obtain deficit (first anomaly). Hence these theories though interesting fail to explain the observed facts and so need not be considered seriously.

(III) The third theory postulates that some of the primary hydrogen liberated at the cathode takes up electrons to become H^- and forms negatively charged microbubbles of hydrogen; they then migrate towards the anode. Similarly positively charged microbubbles of oxygen formed at the anode migrate to the cathode. Our results are not apparently in conflict with this theory because it is conceivable that depolarisers preferentially react and so inhibit formations of these charged microbubbles and so inhibit co-liberation.

However, this theory of counter-migrations of microbubbles does not stand a close examination. Granting that a depolariser consumes the primarily liberated hydrogen or oxygen as the case may be, this theory fails to explain why some oxygen does not appear at the cathode when no hydrogen is liberated at the cathode due to the presence of a depolariser there [Expt. 5 (e)]. Similarly hydrogen should appear in V_A in expt. Nos. 2(a), 2(b), 3 & 4 due to counter migration.

Another strong objection to the counter migration theory is the fact that co-liberation can be demonstrated after a few minutes of electrolysis in suitable systems whereas the calculated time of migration from one electrode to the other is at least a few hours. Also it is difficult to understand from this theory why increase of concentration makes

things Faradaic, other conditions remaining the same. The fact that co-liberation persists even when a cellophane or polyethylene (100Å pore size) membrane is interposed goes against the microbubble idea.

(IV) Some of the objections levelled against the above theory do not apply if instead of microbubbles or ordinary ion it is assumed that the origin of the non-Faradaic behaviour lies in the formation of charged water molecules⁹ (H_2O)_z⁺ near anode and (H_2O)_y⁻ (hydrated electron) near cathode, and these ions move fast to the opposite electrode by electron jump mechanism. The H_2O ⁺ ions react with anions near the cathode liberating oxygen, and the H_2O ⁻ ions react with cations near the anode liberating hydrogen at the anode.

Such a mechanism in essence is electronic conduction, which is generally not considered possible in aqueous systems. However, this theory though has some semblance of a fairly good mechanism and is not against the facts reported in this paper, should be considered yet unproved until some

positive evidence in favour of electronic conduction is forthcoming. Thus the results reported in this paper though highly interesting *vis-a-vis* non-Faradaic electrolysis do not supply the crucial evidence necessary to establish the charged water migration theory or for that matter any of the theories so far proposed.

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